

Studies on Conductance Behavior of *N*-Bromosuccinimide in varying Compositions of Water-DMF at different Temperatures

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The electrical conductance behavior of *N*-bromosuccinimide in water in presence of *N,N*-dimethylformamide has been investigated. The initial increase and later decrease in limiting conductance with DMF hints either the higher ion solvation or the formation of some ionaggregation. The conductance data obtained were analyzed by Debye-Hückel-Onsager and Shedlovsky conductivity models. To establish the formation of ion aggregation ion-equilibria equations have also been used. From the calculated Walden product Stoke's molecular radius is evaluated. Energy of activation of the rate process and related thermodynamic parameters are also computed. All these are used in identifying the nature of ion-solvent interactions involved in the system as a function of temperature.

Frequent use of non-aqueous solvents as media for organic and inorganic reactions has led to increasing interest in the transport properties of electrolytes in solutions. The behavior of electrolytes in solution is revealed by conductance and viscosity investigations which makes one to understand in detail about the nature of ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions^{1,2}. Much importance has been given to the study of conductance behavior of electrolytes in different dipolar aprotic solvents as they are found to be useful for various electrochemical investigations³.

The chemistry of *N*-haloimides has received considerable attention over the years, resulting in substantial advances both in the synthetic and mechanistic aspects⁴. *N*-Bromosuccinimide (NBS) is a good oxidizing agent, which finds applications in organic analysis as brominating agent, in the medicinal field and also as an analytical compound. Kinetic and mechanistic studies of NBS with various substrates have also been carried out⁵. Such a versatile compound did not find any place in literature under the study of electrical conductance or conductivity. This has necessitated the present investigation.

Results and Discussion

Limiting molar conductance : Specific conductance of *N*-bromosuccinimide (in 0, 10, 20, 40 and 60% DMF) was used to compute the molar conductance (Λ_m) and also molar conductance at infinite dilution (Λ_m^0) by Debye-Hückel-Onsager (DHO) and Shedlovsky models of conductivity.

The Λ_m^0 values obtained from DHO models at different compositions of water-dimethylformamide and temperatures are shown in Table 1. As shown in Fig. 1, the DHO plot is slightly non-linear, still extrapolated towards Y-axis to get limiting conductance. Hinatsu and others applied similar principle in their conductance study⁶.

As the DHO plot was non-linear, the obtained limiting conductance may not be the absolute value and its applicability is also questionable. So Shedlovsky model was

Fig. 1. (A) Plots of Λ_m vs \sqrt{C} for NBS in 10% DMF at different temperatures : (\square) 283, (\times) 293, (\circ) 303 and (Δ) 313 K. (B) Plots of Λ_m vs \sqrt{C} for NBS in 20% DMF at different temperatures : (\square) 283, (\times) 293 K, (\circ) 303 and (Δ) 313 K.

applied, which does include corrections for ionic effects, ionic mobilities and ion activity coefficient. This model gives absolute limiting conductance. The Λ_m^0 from DHO model was used as initial limiting conductance in calculating the required data in the Shedlovsky equation,

$$\frac{1}{S\Lambda_m} = \frac{1}{\Lambda_m^0} + \frac{C\Lambda_m S f_{\pm}^2 K_a}{\Lambda_m^0{}^2} \quad (1)$$

where

$$S = \left[\frac{\beta\sqrt{\Lambda_m C}}{2\Lambda_m^0{}^{3/2}} + \sqrt{1 + \frac{\beta^2 C \Lambda_m^2}{4\Lambda_m^0{}^3}} \right]$$

From the intercept of the linear plot of $1/S\Lambda_m$ vs $CA_m S_{\pm}^2$, absolute limiting conductance (Λ_m^0) was determined and the values are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—MEASURED MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AT INFINITE DILUTION (Λ_m^0 , S cm² mol⁻¹) FOR NBS IN WATER AND WATER-DMF MIXTURES (v/v) AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES BY DHO AND SHEDLOVSKY METHOD*

Temp. K	0%		10%		20%		40%	
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
283	43.5	43.4	65.0	64.5	56.6	55.6	37.0	37.0
293	46.5	46.5	84.5	83.3	80.0	80.0	56.5	57.1
303	66.0	66.6	109.0	111.1	103.8	102.0	66.5	66.7
313	80.0	80.0	130.0	133.3	118.0	117.7	90.5	90.9

* (1) = From Λ_m vs \sqrt{C} plot; (2) = from Shedlovsky plot.

As expected Λ_m^0 increased with increase in temperature in all the cases of solvent/solvent mixtures due to the increase in thermal force and hence increased activity or mobility of *N*-bromosuccinimide species. The limiting conductance increased in the beginning (till 10% DMF) and decreased sharply thereafter. Probably neutral NBS molecule has undergone slight dissociation due to incoming organic solvent DMF. It may also be due to breaking down of solvated structure of Br⁺ (of NBS) or the three-dimensional structure of water because of the incoming DMF molecule till 10% DMF. When the amount of DMF increases in the mixture, solvent-solvent interaction increases⁷ and predominates with the formation of some cages for Br⁺ species of NBS, i.e. ion-solvent interaction also increases. The Br⁺ species may also undergo dimerization. All these makes the conductance to decrease from 20 to 40% DMF.

Association/dissociation constant : Association constant of the system was determined from the slope of Shedlovsky plot and are shown in Table 2. Dissociation constant (K_d) was evaluated (Table 2) using Ostwald's dilution law.

TABLE 2—CALCULATED VALUES OF K_a AND K_d FOR NBS IN WATER AND WATER-DMF MIXTURES (v/v) AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. K	$K_a \times 10^3$				$K_d \times 10^{-4}$			
	0%	10%	20%	40%	0%	10%	20%	40%
283	—	5.86	9.29	15.9	—	1.95	—	0.72
293	0.86	6.25	12.3	21.3	13.34	1.81	0.93	0.59
303	1.2	7.12	12.7	17.3	9.68	1.52	0.86	0.66
313	1.3	8.37	11.8	21.4	8.88	1.47	0.96	0.56

This K_d is found to be reciprocal of K_a within the experimental error. Little deviation from ideality is due to wrong assumption of activity coefficient to be unity and the conductance ratio to be equal to degree of dissociation (α). K_a increased with increase in temperature and also with increase in mole fractions of DMF or with the decrease in dielectric constant. The applicability of theory of ion-pair and triplet ion formation was tested at different temperatures by plotting $\log \Lambda_m$ vs $\log C$ on the basis of Fuoss equilibria⁸ equation for partially dissociated electrolytes, which gave straight-line with a slope around

−0.5, as required (for the indication of) the formation of ion-pairs. This proves the presence of ion-pairs or higher ion-solvent interaction in water and ion-pairs with some triplets in water-DMF mixture. The plot of $\Lambda_m \sqrt{C}$ vs C was tried on the basis⁸ of the equation,

$$\Lambda_m \sqrt{C} = \Lambda_m^0 \sqrt{K} + \frac{\Lambda_m^0 \sqrt{K} C}{K_3} \quad (3)$$

where, K is the dissociation constant and K_3 the mass action constant; slope and intercept of this linear plot gives K_3 and K .

The value of $K \times 10^{-4}$ at 303 K is found to be 6.24, 4.13, 0.76 and 0.085 respectively, for 0, 10, 20 and 40% DMF, which is comparable in terms of the order of power with K_d of Table 2. The mass action constant (K_3) is related to the triple ion formation constant. At 303 K, K_3 is found to be 1, 3.8, 1.65 and 1.02 respectively, at 0, 10, 20 and 40% DMF, indicating the presence of ion-association.

Walden product : The product of viscosity of the solvent/solvent mixture and limiting conductance is called Walden product, ($\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0$) which is inversely proportional to the effective radius of ion or species in a given solvent. Table 3 reports the calculated Walden product at all temperatures and solvent compositions. Variation in Walden product with temperature is very small for all the com

TABLE 3—COMPUTED WALDEN PRODUCT ($(\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0, S \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}, \text{poise})$) AND STOKES'S MOLECULAR RADIUS ($r \times 10^{-18} \text{ cm}$) FOR NBS SPECIES IN WATER AND WATER-DMF MIXTURES (v/v)

Temp. K	0%		10%		20%		40%	
	W.P.	r	W.P.	r	W.P.	r	W.P.	r
283	0.56	8.1	1.08	2.7	1.18	2.5	1.21	2.4
293	—	5.9	1.05	2.6	1.28	2.2	1.28	2.2
303	0.53	5.1	1.11	2.4	1.23	2.2	1.16	2.3
313	0.52	5.0	1.07	2.5	1.14	2.3	1.25	2.2

positions, therefore, Stoke's molecular radius r ($\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0 \propto 1/r$) will not change with temperature. Product increased with increase in DMF content, i.e. the effect of variation in limiting conductance is not nullified by the variation in viscosity. Computed Stoke's radius is given in Table 3. The variation in Walden product and Stoke's molecular radius hints at the solvation behavior of the ion by the solvent/solvent mixtures. Indirectly, it also tells about the solvent-solvent interaction and their role in the mobility of the ionic species. Cation of *N*-bromosuccinimide is preferentially solvated by water compared to bulky DMF solvent molecules. At higher DMF content, the DMF molecule itself is taking part in solvating the anion of NBS. It can be predicted that the structure of water determines the Walden product in water-DMF mixture. The structure of water gets altered either because of solvent-solvent or ion-solvent interactions or both put together. Abrupt variation in R_x [$R_x = (\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0) \text{ solvent mix} / (\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0) \text{ solvent}$] was observed^{2,8} on adding a non-polar solvent (DMF) to a polar solvent mixture. It is a strong indication of the preferential solvation of the electrolyte/ion by the solvent in these mixtures.

Thermodynamic parameters : Energy of activation (E_a) of the rate process can be determined by equating limiting conductance to the rate process. Hence the Arrhenius equation, $\Lambda_m^0 = A e^{-E_a/RT}$ can be used for the purpose. From the slope of the linear plot of $\log \Lambda_m^0$ vs T^{-1} the value of E_a has been estimated and presented in Table 4. It increased with increase in DMF as expected. The values of $\log A$ obtained from the intercept of the above plot is almost a constant, proposing smaller electrostatic interaction.

TABLE 4—COMPUTED THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR NBS UNDER VARYING COMPOSITIONS OF WATER-DMF MIXTURE (v/v)

Parameter	0%	10%	20%	40%
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	14.9	18.4	18.8	19.5
$\log A$	1.8	2.0	2.0	1.8
ΔH_a^0 (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-11.4	-9.0	-8.4	-7.4
ΔS_a^0 (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	18	33	49	56
ΔG_a^0 (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-17.5	-21.5	-23.1	-24.3

$\log K_a$ was plotted against reciprocal of temperature (figure not shown), the slope of which yielded $\Delta H_a^0/2.303R$, and hence ΔH_a^0 , the change of the enthalpy of association, was calculated and found to be exothermic in character. Enthalpy of association (ΔH_a^0), of the process decreased from 0 to 40% DMF, which is in accordance with the obtained limiting conductance value (Table 1). The negative value for ΔH_a^0 is attributed⁹ to the existence of short range forces, which is an indication of ion-association.

The association process is further probed by the change in free energy value (ΔG_a^0), which is calculated from $\Delta G_a^0 = RT \ln K_a$. It is the change in free energy that occurs when an ion is moved from gaseous state to a solvent or from one solvent to another. The negative sign indicates the increased stability of the species in that medium. So stability of the species in the medium can be identified by the negative value of ΔG_a^0 . It has been calculated at all temperatures, the mean value calculated is shown in Table 4, ΔG_a^0 is found to be negative supporting our prediction of ion-association. That means, the species not only undergo association but they are stable in solvent mixture and that too increases with increase in % DMF.

Entropy of association is also calculated from the equation $(\Delta H_a^0 - \Delta G_a^0)/T$ at each temperature and the mean has been determined at different compositions (Table 4). ΔH_a^0 is small, positive and increasing from 0 to 40% DMF indicating the increased electrostriction or slight disorderness in the process. Probably this favours the association process proposed earlier.

The small entropy values of association suggest the

specific interaction required steric restriction for the formation of contact ion-pair or ion-association. Entropy is significantly connected with the solvent structure perturbation brought about by the disordered ions. The small positive ΔS_a^0 has been considered¹⁰ as due to the decreased orientation of water molecules and the ion-pairs formed. The small ΔS_a^0 values also suggest that the ion-association occurs without the release of hydration of water molecules from the complex structure.

Experimental

Dimethylformamide (Qualigens) was dried using 4A molecular sieve and distilled under reduced pressure at 45°. Triple-distilled water was used throughout. The specific conductivity of the purified solvent and water were of the order 10⁻⁷ S cm⁻¹. The purity of solvents was checked from their physical parameters at 298 K. *N*-Bromosuccinimide (Sisco, A.R.) was used as electrolyte, and its stock solution (0.1 M) in water-DMF mixture was prepared and standardized iodometrically. NBS solution was freshly prepared and stored in coloured bottles.

Conductance was measured with an Elico CM-180 instrument. A dip type conductivity cell with platinized electrodes was calibrated (cell constant = 0.999 cm⁻¹). All the measurements were made in a thermostat ($\pm 0.01^\circ$), the instrument was standardized as usual. A solution of known concentration was taken in a double-walled vessel and thermostated for about 20–30 min and its specific conductivity noted. Number of trials were done for the consistency of the value and the final/average value was taken.

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